

宇宙起源基能模型

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摘要：提出一个宇宙起源的理论模型，宇宙起源基能模型，和原初宇宙、史前宇宙的概念。宇宙起源基能模型认为，原初宇宙即起始时期的宇宙，是由基能即无序运动的能量组成的。并认为原初宇宙不是密度无限大的奇点，具有有限的体积、半径和密度，其体积由原初宇宙质量、原初宇宙引力与被压缩基能产生的反作用力共同确定。与原初宇宙引力平衡的作用力是被压缩基能产生的反作用力。其研究表明，原初宇宙本身就是一个超级大黑洞；同时表明原初宇宙外必然存在其它物质；也可能存在着多个宇宙；当前的宇宙有可能是振荡型的振荡宇宙；各种宇宙中都不存在密度无限大的奇点。原初宇宙爆炸产生的定向运动是现代宇宙中物质有序性产生的根源。提出一个宇宙总质量的大小是由其引力的最大束缚能力决定的观点。可解释宇宙大爆炸的起始原因。并给出原初宇宙具有有限体积和基能存在的可靠证据。

关键词：宇宙起源基能模型，基能，原初宇宙，史前宇宙，振荡宇宙，黑洞

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宇宙起源的大爆炸理论模型认为，现代宇宙起源于一个密度无限大的奇点发生的大爆炸。霍金认为，如果爱因斯坦的广义相对论是正确的，就存在一个奇点，这是具有无限密度和无限时空曲率的点，时间在那里有一个开端。彭罗斯和霍金的奇性定理预言，宇宙有一个开端。这些定理并没有告诉宇宙是如何起始的[1]。

在黑洞组成和结构[2]、光子结构[3]、电子和正电子及强子结构[4-6]研究的基础上，我们提出一个宇宙起源的理论模型，宇宙起源基能模型或称宇宙起源模型，认为宇宙是由能量组成的，有序的物质只是能量的存在模式或方式之一，当前宇宙起源时期的状态，称为原初宇宙，是由基能即无序运动的能量组成的。并且认为原初宇宙不是密度无限大的奇点，具有有限的体积、半径和密度，其体积由原初宇宙质量、原初宇宙引力与被压缩基能产生的反作用力共同确定。原初宇宙本身就是一个超级大黑洞。与原初宇宙引力平衡的作用力是被压缩基能产生的反作用力。基能的抗压缩力应该是没有上限的，或者是上限值非常大足以抗衡施加的任何压力，包括原初宇宙的压力。原初宇宙引力的束缚作用和作用范围都是有限的，不是无限的。

已知的所有实验结果都已经证明强和弱相互作用的束缚作用和作用范围都是有限的。我们认为电磁相互作用的束缚作用和作用范围也都是有限的。与此类似，引力的束缚作用和作用范围不应该是无限的。宇宙起源模型的研究结果表明，由基能组成的原初宇宙，其结构原本就应该是一个最大的大黑洞，与普通黑洞相比除了质量更大以外没有本质上的差别。

宇宙起源模型认为，比原初宇宙存在时期更早的宇宙，称为史前宇宙，由于

它极其巨大的引力，能够吸收大量的物质和能量包括基能，当吸收的这些物质和能量的总量接近或达到史前宇宙引力的束缚能力的极限时，史前宇宙就会变得不稳定，宇宙演化就从史前宇宙时期到了原初宇宙时期，继续吸收更多的物质和能量，引发了原初宇宙的大爆炸并进而演化成现代的宇宙。这应能表明引力束缚能力的大小与宇宙的大小是密切相关的。同时表明原初宇宙外必然存在其它宇宙和物质。推论，一个宇宙应该是引力的最大束缚能力所能束缚的物质和能量的总量的一个单元或一个单位。或者表述为一个宇宙总质量的大小是由其引力的最大束缚能力决定的。

与史前宇宙和原初宇宙演化情况类似的现象，是原子核以及增加原子核中核子个数引起其稳定性的变化情况。原子核中的核子是依靠强相互作用束缚在一起的。强相互作用的束缚作用和作用范围都是有限的。当原子核中的核子个数较少时，原子核可以继续吸收核子，并且能够稳定的存在，但是当核内核子总数达到一定值后，接近或达到核力的最大束缚能力时，原子核就变得不稳定，如果再吸收核子，则整个原子核就有可能发生裂变而破裂，也可称为爆炸。

原初宇宙爆炸的原因，我们认为是原初宇宙的引力与被压缩基能的反作用力之间有一个平衡机制，当原初宇宙吸收物质质量和基能的总量达到一定程度时，就破坏了这种平衡机制，超出了其最大承载能力，也超过了其引力的最大束缚能力，从而引发原初宇宙的爆炸。这也解释了宇宙大爆炸的起始原因、宇宙起源过程和机理。

宇宙起源模型给出的结果，支持振荡型宇宙或振荡宇宙假设，即宇宙演化是沿着收缩到极点就爆发膨胀，膨胀到极点就收缩，这样一个由收缩和膨胀组成的循环过程。当向外持续膨胀物质的动能被引力全部消耗掉时，宇宙将开始收缩过程。引力如何在遥远天体间发生作用，以及如何传递这些相互作用，仍然需要进一步的研究。例如，引力作用距离是有限的还是无限的？即使引力作用距离是有限的，只要其远大于宇宙膨胀物质能够达到的最大距离，宇宙就必然在膨胀到最大后开始其收缩过程。但这种振荡过程将是一个极其漫长或最漫长的过程。也不能排除宇宙膨胀物质能够达到的最大距离远大于宇宙引力作用距离的情况，这种情况下膨胀物质应该持续膨胀，将会一直膨胀到与其它膨胀的宇宙相交叉重叠，直到最后为其它的宇宙吸收。其前提是，不同的宇宙遵循的原理应该是相同的。这表明该模型也支持持续膨胀宇宙。关键在于宇宙引力作用距离与宇宙膨胀物质能够达到的最大距离那一个更大。这也进一步表明，一个宇宙就是一个引力单元的观点或基本假设是合理的。

如果宇宙起源模型是正确的，则普通黑洞，例如银河系核心黑洞等，不会爆炸，因为这类依靠相同引力束缚的黑洞的质量，还远没有达到原初宇宙大爆炸时总基能的值，因此都是稳定的。

现代宇宙中有许多物质及其存在状态都是有序的。例如原子及其量子化的能量态。这些物质有序性的根本起源。宇宙起源模型认为是原初宇宙爆炸时产生的定向运动导致了这些有序性的产生。这种定向运动产生的有序性，使得原初宇宙中的能量从全部无序状态转变成现代宇宙中能量的部分有序、部分仍然无序的状态。进一步产生物质及其存在状态有序性的其它机制和具体过程，例如各种粒子的产生机制和过程，都在深入研究中。

宇宙起源模型表明，有人类生存的这个宇宙是有限的，因为爆炸所及是有限的，可能也不是唯一的，不能排除存在许多同样或类似的宇宙的可能性。

宇宙起源模型给出结论的可能证据和验证方法。例如，通过引力波的观测，有可能探测到宇宙外其它宇宙中发生的重大引力变化事件。例如宇宙外原初宇宙的大爆炸事件。但这种超级大爆炸事件发生的概率太低，很难探测到。如果这种超级大爆炸事件的引力波结果能被观测到，就有可能直接证实宇宙外宇宙的存在性。因为不同宇宙间的引力波应该能相互传播并产生影响。引力波传播的速度又远远大于大爆炸物质膨胀传播的速度。因此，引力波在不同宇宙间传播应该是可能的。当然，也不能排除宇宙外文明存在的可能性。

总结，提出的宇宙起源基能模型表明，宇宙与基能密切相关。原初宇宙的巨引力能破坏所有有序物质的有序性，其包含的能量是处于无序运动状态，应该全部是基能，并且是基能的超高密度状态。综合研究结论表明原初宇宙不是密度无限大的奇点，具有有限的体积、半径和密度，其体积由原初宇宙质量、原初宇宙引力与基能抗压缩力确定。与原初宇宙引力平衡的作用力是被压缩基能产生的反作用力。原初宇宙本身就是一个超级大黑洞。同时表明原初宇宙外必然存在其它物质。也可能存在着多个宇宙。当前的宇宙有可能是振荡型的。各种宇宙中都不存在密度无限大的奇点。恒星、白矮星、中子星都是由有序运动能量即基能的有序运动构成的物质组成的，而原初宇宙与黑洞一样是由无序运动能量即基能构成的。并基于黑洞具有角动量和稳定存在的两极，推论出史前宇宙、原初宇宙都可能在转运并具有角动量和稳定存在的两极，应该可以作为其具有有限体积的直接证据。同时基于光子结构研究结果给出基能存在的可靠证据。

Jineng model of origin of the Universe

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Abstract

We present a theoretical model of the origin of the Universe, the Jineng model of origin of the Universe and the concepts of the initial Universe, prehistorical Universe, and Jineng. This model indicates the initial Universe, namely the Universe during its initial period, is composed of Jineng namely the random motion energy. And it thoughts the initial Universe is not a singular point with infinite density, it possesses limited volume, radius and density, its volume is determined by the initial Universe mass, the initial Universe gravitational force and the counterforce produced by the compressed Jineng together. The acting force balancing with the initial Universe gravitational force is the counterforce produced by the compressed Jineng. Its research results indicate that the initial Universe itself must be a super big black hole. Simultaneously it indicates there must exist other matter outside the initial Universe. There could be many Universes in existence. The modern Universe could be a oscillating Universe or a continuously expanding Universe, and their possible reason. There is no any singular point with infinite density among all of different kinds of Universes. The directional motions created by the initial Universe explosion is the root to create the ordered nature of matter in the modern Universe. We present a point of view that the size of total mass of a single Universe is determined by the maximum binding ability produced by its gravitational force. And the reliable evidences of the initial Universe with limited volume and its possible reason and mechanism to explode, and Jineng in existence, are presented.

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Keywords: Jineng model of origin of the Universe, Jineng, black hole, initial Universe, prehistorical Universe, oscillating Universe, continuously expanding Universe

The Big Bang theoretical model of origin of the Universe thoughts the origin of the modern Universe is a Big Bang occurred by a singular point with infinite density. Hawking thoughts, if Einstein's theory of general relativity is correct, then there is existing a singular point with infinite density and infinite space-time curvature, and the time begins there [1]. Hawking and Penrose singularity theorem predicted that the Universe has a beginning or origin, and this theorem has not explained how about the Universe began [1].

Based on the investigation of the black hole component and structure [2], photon structure [3], electron and positron, hadron structure [4–6], we present a kind of theoretical model of the origin of the Universe, the Jineng model of Origin of the Universe (DOU), or named as the cosmic origin Jineng model. DOU thoughts the Universe is composed of energy, the ordered substance and matter is just one of the existing modes of energy, the state of the origin period of the current Universe, referred to as the initial Universe, is composed of Jineng namely the random motion energy. And it thoughts the initial Universe is not a singular point with infinite density, it possesses limited volume, radius and density, its volume is determined by the initial Universe mass, the initial Universe gravitational force and the counterforce produced by the compressed Jineng together. The initial Universe itself just is a super big black hole. The acting force balancing with the initial Universe gravitational force is the counterforce produced by the compressed Jineng. There should be no upper limit for the force of resisting compression of Jineng, or its upper limit value is large enough to counter balance the applied any pressure, include the pressure of the initial Universe. The binding action and controlling range of gravitational force of the initial Universe is limited, not infinite.

All of known experimental results have proved and demonstrated that the binding action and controlling range of the strong and weak interaction are all limited. We think or consider that the binding action and controlling range of the electromagnetic interaction are all limited too. Similarly, the binding action and controlling range of gravitational force should not be infinite. The DOU research results indicate that the initial Universe is composed of Jineng, its structure itself should be a maximal big black hole, as compared to the common black holes except with much more mass, there is no natural difference.

DOU thoughts, the Universe which is still earlier than the initial Universe existing period is referred to as the prehistorical Universe, owing to its most huge gravitational force, can absorb vast matter and energy including Jineng, when the total amount of these absorbed

matter and energy approaches or reaches up to the binding ability limit of the prehistorical Universe gravitational force, the prehistorical Universe would become instable, the Universe evolution will enter from the prehistorical Universe period into the initial Universe period, continue to absorb more matter and energy, cause the initial Universe to explode or form the Big Bang, and its further evolution becomes the modern Universe. These results should be able to demonstrate that the size of binding ability of gravitational force is closely related to the size of the Universe. Simultaneously it indicates there must exist other Universes and matter outside the initial Universe. The deduction, one Universe should be one unit of total amount of matter and energy bound by the maximal binding ability of gravitational force. It can be expressed that the size of total mass of a single Universe is determined by the maximum binding ability produced by its gravitational force.

The phenomenon which is similar to the prehistorical Universe and the initial Universe evolution situation is nuclei as well as increasing the nucleon number in nuclei to cause the change situation of nuclear stability. Binding nucleons in nuclei to keep together depends on the strong interaction. Because the binding action and controlling range of the strong interaction are all limited, when the number of nucleons in nuclei is less, the nuclei could continue to absorb nucleons and can exist stably, but when the total nucleons in the nuclei reach to a definite value, approach or reach up to the maximal binding ability of nuclear force, the nuclei will become instable, continue to absorb more nucleons, then the whole nuclei would occur fission whereas broken, also can be referred to as explosion.

For the explosive reason of the initial Universe, we think there is a balancing mechanism between the gravitational force of the initial Universe and the counterforce of the compressed Jineng, when the total amount of matter mass and Jineng absorbed by the initial Universe reaches up to a certain degree, the balancing mechanism would be destroyed, exceed its maximal carrying capacity, also exceed the maximal binding ability of its gravitational force, thereby cause the initial Universe to explode. This also explains the beginning reason of the Big Bang, the procedure and mechanism of the origin of the Universe.

The results shown by DOU support the oscillatory mode Universe or oscillating Universe assumption, namely the Universe evolution is along with shrinking to the limit then exploding and expanding, expanding to the limit then shrinking, such a cyclical process composed of shrinkage and expansion. When the kinetic energy of continuously expanding matter is used up by its gravitational force wholly, the Universe would begin a shrinking

procedure. How about the gravitational force plays a role among remote celestial bodies, as well as these interactions propagate, further researches are needed still. For example, the interacting distance of gravitational force is limited or infinite? Even if the gravitational interaction distance is limited, as long as it is far larger than the maximum distance to which the cosmic expansion matter can reach up, the Universe must begin its shrinking procedure after it expands to the maximum. But such kind of oscillating process will be an extremely long procedure or the most long procedure. The case or situation should not be excluded that the maximum distance possibly reached by the cosmic expansion matter is far larger than the maximum distance of Universe gravitational force interaction, under this condition, the expanding matter should continue to expand, until across and overlap with other expanding Universes, and at last absorbed by other Universes. The precondition is the principles obeyed by different Universes should be the same.

This indicates that DOU supports the continuously expanding Universe too. The key point is which is the larger between the maximum distance possibly reached by the cosmic expansion matter and the maximum distance of Universe gravitational force interaction. This further indicates that the point of view or basic assumption, one Universe just is one gravitational force unit, is reasonable.

If DOU is correct, then common black holes, for instance the black hole located at the galactic center, would not explode, because the mass of this type of black holes depending on the same gravitational force, does not reach the value of total Jineng of the Big Bang of the initial Universe, therefore all of them are stable.

There are many matter and substance and their existing states in the modern Universe is all ordered. For instance atoms and their quantized energy states. DOU considers, the root origin of the ordered properties or features of these matter is that the directional motion produced by the initial Universe explosion results in the creation of these ordered features. The ordered features produced by such kind of directional motion, make the energy inside the initial Universe from the wholly random state become into parts in the ordered states and parts still in the random states in the modern Universe. Other mechanisms and actually detailed procedures of further creating matter and its existing states, for instance the creating mechanism and procedure of different kinds of particles, are all investigated deeply in the world.

DOU demonstrates, the human living Universe is limited, because the explosion

region is limited, could not be unique or only, can not exclude the feasibility of existing many same or similar Universes.

The possible evidences and verification methods of the DOU conclusions obtained can be tested. For example, via the observation of gravitational waves, one could detect the great important gravitational force change events occurred in other Universes outside our Universe. For instance, one can detect the Big Bang events of the initial Universe outside our Universe. But the happening probability of such kind of super big bang events is too low, it is difficult to detect them. In case the gravitational wave results of such kinds of super big bang events could be observed, it would directly confirm other Universe existence outside our Universe, because the gravitational waves among or within different Universes should propagate and make effects mutually. The propagating velocity of gravitational waves is much greater than the expanding velocity of matter due to the Big Bang. Therefore, the gravitational waves propagate among different Universes should be possible and feasible. Of course, the feasibility of civilization in existence outside our Universe could not be excluded.

In summary, the presented DOU demonstrates that the Universe and Jineng are closely relate to each other. The huge gravitational force of the initial Universe can destroy the ordered features of all of ordered matter, its included energy exists in a state of random motion, should be Jineng wholly, and is the super high density state of Jineng. DOU comprehensive research conclusions indicate the initial Universe is not a singular point with infinite density, it possesses limited volume, radius and density, its volume is determined by the initial Universe mass, the initial Universe gravitational force and the counterforce produced by the compressed Jineng together. The acting force balancing with the initial Universe gravitational force is the counterforce produced by the compressed Jineng. The initial Universe itself just is a super big black hole. Simultaneously it indicates there must exist other matter outside the initial Universe. There could be many Universes in existence. The modern Universe may be a oscillating Universe or a continuously expanding Universe, and the reason is shown. There is no any singular point with infinite density among all of different kinds of Universes. The possible reason and mechanism to cause the initial Universe Big Bang is suggested. Stars, white dwarfs, neutron stars are all composed of the matter formed by the ordered motion energy namely the ordered motion of Jineng, whereas the initial Universe which is the same as common black holes, is composed of the random motion energy namely Jineng. And based on black holes possess angular momentum and the

stable two poles in existence, we deduce all the prehistorical Universe, the initial Universe could rotate and possess angular momentum and the stable two poles in existence, it should act as the direct evidence of the initial Universe possessing limited volume. Simultaneously, based on the research results of photon structure, we show the reliable evidence of Jineng in existence.

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